

Literature review on the diverse perspectives on fisheries at the global scale

Overview of documents with codes for figures 2.36 – 2.41 shown in annex 2.12

Documents with code - Justice

	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage (valid)
Distributional	42	32,81	64,62
Procedural	33	25,78	50,77
Recognitional	16	12,50	24,62
DOCUMENTS with code(s)	65	50,78	100,00
DOCUMENTS without code(s)	63	49,22	-
ANALYZED DOCUMENTS	128	100,00	-

Documents with code - Power Dynamics

	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage (valid)
Interaction	51	39,84	58,62
Material	44	34,38	50,57
Rule-making	33	25,78	37,93
Framing	18	14,06	20,69
Discursive	10	7,81	11,49
DOCUMENTS with code(s)	87	67,97	100,00
DOCUMENTS without code(s)	41	32,03	-
ANALYZED DOCUMENTS	128	100,00	-

Documents with code - Specific Values Present

	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage (valid)
Instrumental	57	44,53	81,43
Relational	22	17,19	31,43
Intrinsic	4	3,13	5,71
DOCUMENTS with code(s)	70	54,69	100,00
DOCUMENTS without code(s)	58	45,31	-
ANALYZED DOCUMENTS	128	100,00	-

Documents with code - Value Indicators Used

	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage (valid)
Monetary	60	46,88	71,43
Socio-cultural	36	28,13	42,86
Biophysical	29	22,66	34,52
DOCUMENTS with code(s)	84	65,63	100,00
DOCUMENTS without code(s)	44	34,38	-
ANALYZED DOCUMENTS	128	100,00	-

Documents with code - Valuation Targets

	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage (valid)
Material NCP	53	41,41	80,30
Quality of life	19	14,84	28,79
Non-Material NCP	17	13,28	25,76
Nature	6	4,69	9,09
Regulating NCP	3	2,34	4,55
DOCUMENTS with code(s)	66	51,56	100,00
DOCUMENTS without code(s)	62	48,44	-
ANALYZED DOCUMENTS	128	100,00	-

Documents with code - Decision-Making Typology

	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage (valid)
Political (+)	31	24,22	48,44
Economic (+)	31	24,22	48,44
Socio-environmental (+)	25	19,53	39,06
DOCUMENTS with code(s)	64	50,00	100,00
DOCUMENTS without code(s)	64	50,00	-
ANALYZED DOCUMENTS	128	100,00	-